

Thermogravimetry of Reclaimed Rubber Compounds

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Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out for reclaimed rubber and its compounds under different perspectives. Study on degradation characteristics was the principal object in the present series of experiments.

THERMAL analysis finds frequent use in the investigations of the influence of various factors on the thermogram characteristics of different elastomer systems^{1,2}. Some results on differential thermal analysis (DTA) of reclaimed rubber compounds have been reported earlier^{3,4,5}. The present communication deals with the thermogravimetric (TGA) studies on (a) compounds based separately on reclaimed rubber, natural rubber (NR) and reclaim-NR blend, (b) two different reclaims, and (c) effect of (i) sulphur, (ii) zinc oxide, and (iii) accelerator in a reclaim compound.

The TGA studies were carried out in a TGA apparatus fabricated in our laboratory. Temperature calibration corresponding to weight loss for the whole temperature range of interest was made by using known systems.

The recipe of the compounds [high-sulphur, containing the limiting proportion of sulphur (50 parts)^{6,7}] is shown in Table I and their TGA thermograms in

whereas curve II stands for the compound based on their blend (ratio of hydrocarbon content=50 : 50). Among these three systems some identity is observed upto the temperature region of 200°, no weight loss being exhibited so long. Above this temperature zone each of the systems starts losing weight, the rates of loss varying in some extent from each other in the three cases. These present rates break above 250° and new rates are observed for all these systems, and found to follow parallel relations. Around 350°, weight loss starts at much faster rates as compared to the previous rates. Also the differences among the rates of the three systems at this stage are significantly greater than those noted previously. So far as this last section of these TGA curves are concerned, the difference between the rates of the NR-based and the reclaim-NR-blend-based compounds is, to a considerable extent, greater than that between the rates of compounds based on reclaim-NR blend and reclaim respectively. For all the three systems a tendency in the change of the rate of weight loss is observed above 400°.

TABLE I

Formulation of Compounds* (parts by weight) analyzed by TGA

	I	II	III
Smoked sheet	100.0	50.0	—
Reclaim.	—	100.00	200.0
Stearic acid	1.0	1.0	1.0
Zinc oxide	5.0	5.0	5.0
BA**	1.0	1.0	1.0
Sulphur	50.0	50.0	50.0

* The reclaim contains about 50% of rubber hydrocarbon. Therefore, the proportion of reclaim used is twice that of smoked sheet to be substituted.

** Butylaldehyde aniline.

Fig. 1.: TGA curves for compounds based on natural rubber, natural rubber—reclaim blend and reclaim.

Figure 1. Curves I and III represent compounds based solely on natural rubber and reclaim respectively,

All these reveal the diminution in the tendency of degradation of natural rubber by incorporation of reclaim—a notable beneficial effect of reclaim for practical compounds and further supported in the DTA studies⁹.

Two different reclaims (as manufactured by two different manufacturers) were compared by TGA. The specifications of the pair of reclaims are shown in Table 2 and their TGA thermograms in Figure 2. Curves marked as reclaim A and reclaim B represent the two reclaims. From these two systems it is revealed that upto the temperature region around 250° neither of the reclaims exhibit any loss in weight. Above this temperature zone both the systems lose weight gradually, the rate of loss being higher for one reclaim (reclaim A) than that for the other one (reclaim B). Both the reclaims show at temperatures above 350° their weight loss at rates much different from and higher than the previous rates, but above 350° at initial stage the weight loss for reclaim B proceeds at a higher rate than that for reclaim A and ultimately almost overlap.

TABLE 2—COMMERCIAL DATA SPECIFYING THE RECLAIMS.

	Ash	%Acetone extract, %	Carbon Black, %	Rubber Hydrocarbon by difference ; %
Reclaim A (WTR 100)	10±2	14±4	22±4	Not less than 50
Reclaim B (WTS)	5-8	14-18	22-25	52-55

Fig. 2. : TGA curves of a pair of reclaims.

The above pair of reclaims (A and B) were also compared by DTA. The DTA thermograms are shown in Figure 3, where curves marked as reclaim A and reclaim B represent the two reclaims. It is found that the peak area and peak height of reclaim A is appreciably greater than those of reclaim B. Whereas initial

temperature of reclaim A is lower than that of the other, their peak temperatures are also somewhat different. On the other hand, slope of reclaim A is, to a considerable extent, higher than that of reclaim B and for both the reclaims some peaks are present in the high-temperature regions although in varying prominences.

Fig. 3. : DTA curves of the pair of reclaims.

These studies indicated that the reclaim A had a much more affinity towards degradation than the reclaim B and hence the former contained more of natural rubber, and the latter more of styrene-butadiene rubber, predictable from the relative characteristics of these polymers⁹.

Effect of Sulphur :

Table 3 represents the recipes of the compounds whose TGA thermograms are shown in Figure 4. Curves I and II represent respectively the high- and the

TABLE 3

Formulation of Compounds* (parts by weight) analysed by TGA

	I	II
Reclaim	100.0	100.0
Stearic Acid	0.5	0.5
Zinc Oxide	2.5	2.5
TMTD**	0.5	0.5
Sulphur	25.0	1.5

* Formulations are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim.

** Tetramethylthiuram disulphide.

low - sulphur compounds. Upto the temperature region around 200° practically no weight loss takes place for

any of these systems. But in both cases weight loss is initiated above that temperature zone. The rate of loss in case of the high-sulphur compound is, however, much higher than that for the low-sulphur one. Above 250° a break in such rates is found in both the compounds with more prominence in the high-sulphur one, allowing new rates to follow. Further change in the rates of weight loss occurs above 350° for both the systems and the rates of each of the two at this stage are appreciably greater than the previous rates of the corresponding systems. In the high-sulphur compound the rate of loss once more tends to change above 400°.

Fig. 4. : TGA curves of high- and low- sulphur compounds based on reclaim.

All these show, in general, the diminution in the affinity towards degradation with increasing sulphur content.

Effect of Zinc Oxide :

The recipes of the compounds are shown in Table 4, their TGA thermograms being shown in Figure 5. Curves a and b represent respectively the compounds in absence and in presence of zinc oxide. Both the systems indicate, beside little differences at different temperature zones, similar characteristics regarding the rates of weight loss.

TABLE 4
Formulation of Compounds* (parts by weight) analysed by TGA

	A	B
Reclaim	100.0	100.0
Stearic acid	0.5	0.5
Zinc oxide	—	2.5
BA	0.5	0.5
Sulphur	25.0	25.0

* Formulations are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim.

Fig. 5. : TGA curves of reclaim compounds with and without Zinc oxide.

Thus the incorporation of zinc oxide in a high-sulphur compound did not show any effect towards its thermal stability, as also supported by DTA studies⁴.

Effect of Accelerator :

Table 5 displays the recipes of the compounds, whose TGA thermograms are shown in Figure 6. Curves a and b represent respectively the compounds with two different types of accelerators, BA and TMTD. At different temperature zones some differences were observed, otherwise characteristics exhibited were similar for both the systems. In both cases loss of weight practically starts only above the temperature region around 200°. Above 250° there is a break in the rate of weight loss. This break is, however, more prominent

TABLE 5

Formulation of Compounds* (parts by weight) analysed by TGA

	a	b.
Reclaim	100.0	100.0
Stearic acid	0.5	0.5
Zinc Oxide	2.5	2.5
BA	0.5	—
TMTD	—	0.5
Sulphur	25.0	25.0

* Formulations are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim.

in the BA-containing compound than in the one containing TMTD. For both the systems the rate of weight loss significantly changes above 350° and these new rates

are found to proceed almost in parallel. Above 400° a further tendency of the change of rate is observed.

Fig. 6. : TGA curves of reclaim compounds with different accelerators.

This reveals, in general, that irrespective of the type of accelerator used high-sulphur reclaim compounds exhibit a similar trend towards their thermal stability characteristics.

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